

A Systematic Review on Siddha Metallo-mineral Formulation – Thiruvanga Chunnam

Dr.N.Thamizh Bharathi^{1*}, Dr.M.Prasanna², R.Madhavan³

¹ PG Scholar, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam, National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium (Affiliated to TN Dr MGR Medical University, Chennai)

² PG Scholar, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam, National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium (Affiliated to TN Dr MGR Medical University, Chennai)

³ Professor and Head of the Department, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam, National Institute of Siddha, Tambaram Sanatorium (Affiliated to TN Dr MGR Medical University, Chennai)

*Address for Correspondence:

Dr.N.Thamizh Bharathi
PG Scholar, Department of Nanju Maruthuvam,
National Institute of Siddha, (Affiliated to TN Dr MGR Medical University, Chennai)
Tambaram Sanatorium

ABSTRACT:

Background: *Thiruvanga Chunnam*, a metallo-mineral formulation in Siddha medicine, has been traditionally employed in the treatment of paralysis, Diabetes mellitus, Diabetes insipidus, Carbuncles etc,. Despite its long-standing use, scientific evaluation and systematic evidence remain limited. **Methods:** A systematic review was carried out by literature searched from 2019–2025 in PubMed, Google Scholar, AYUSH Research Portal, and other databases. Siddha classical texts were also referred to for traditional indications. Inclusion criteria covered studies on purification, preparation, pharmacological, and toxicological evaluations of *Thiruvanga Chunnam* and its ingredients. **Results:** *Thiruvanga Chunnam* is prepared using purified Tin, Stannum, mercury, and zinc with herbal ingredients. Modern studies highlight its pharmacological actions, including antioxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and cytoprotective activities. Plant ingredients also exhibit synergistic pharmacological effects that support Siddha claims. Safety concerns regarding metallic formulations are addressed through traditional

purification methods though comprehensive toxicological validation is still needed. **Conclusion:** Thus, the available evidence supports its wide therapeutic potential, but standardized clinical and toxicological studies are essential to ensure safe integration into contemporary healthcare.

Keywords: Chunnam, Thiruvanga Chunnam, Systematic Review, Siddha Medicine

1 INTRODUCTION:

The Siddha system of medicine, a traditional medical practice predominantly followed in Tamil Nadu, is founded on a holistic philosophical framework that integrates natural elements for therapeutic purposes based on *Panchabootha* philosophy [1]. Its pharmacopeia encompasses a diverse range of medicinal formulations derived from herbal, metallic, mineral, and animal sources [1]. Treatments in Siddha medicine are broadly categorized into internal and external medicines, further subdivided into 32 distinct dosage forms, each characterized by specific preparation methods, stability, and therapeutic properties [2]. Among the 24 documented preparation types in classical literature, *Chunnam* (caustic alkali) occupies a unique position [3]. *Chunnam* is prepared through a careful process involving the trituration of mercury or other metals, either individually or in combination with herbal juices, to create a specific formulation. This mixture is then placed in a mud pot, sealed with mud-pasted cloth, and subjected to controlled incineration, yielding a fine white powder upon cooling [4, 5]. The term *chunnam*, literally meaning “white lime” in Tamil, refers to an alkaline, caustic preparation similar to slaked lime. This dosage form is considered superior in potency and therapeutic significance compared to other high-potency Siddha formulations such as *Parpam* and *Chenduram* [6]. One of its remarkable attributes is its extraordinary shelf life, documented to remain stable for up to 500 years, allowing for long-term preservation without loss of efficacy. *Chunnam* preparations are therapeutically potent even in minimal doses, reflecting their concentrated pharmacological activity [5]. Specifically, *Thiruvanga Chunnam* is a specialized formulation in which purified mercury, tin, stannum and zinc are utilized. It represents the complex amalgamation of metallic and herbal principles in Siddha pharmaceutics and is traditionally employed for its potent therapeutic actions, including anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, and other systemic benefits.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

The literature search was conducted across multiple electronic databases, including PubMed, Google Scholar, Wiley Online Library, ScienceDirect, ACS Publications, Springer Link, Semantic Scholar, and Embase. A wide range of keywords and their combinations were applied, such as “*Karuvangam*,” “*Velvangam*,” “*Rasam*,” “*Naagam*,” “*Madhuca longifolia*,” “*Pergularia daemia*,” “*Acalypha indica*,” “*Phyllanthus niruri*,” along with pharmacological terms including “hepatoprotective,” “antiulcer,” “antioxidant,” “anti-inflammatory,” “analgesic,” “antinociceptive,” “anticancer,” “anti-arthritis,” “antibacterial,” “antidiabetic,” “antimicrobial,” and “anthelmintic.” Additional emphasis was given to search terms related to pharmacological activities, ethnopharmacology, Siddha medicine.

The review focused on studies published between 2019 and 2025, and the entire screening and analysis process extended over six months. Eligible studies were selected based on their relevance to the ingredients of *Thiruvanga Chunnam* and its therapeutic applications, as well as the availability of full-text articles. Study types considered included clinical trials, experimental investigations, and review papers. Publications were excluded if they were duplicates, irrelevant, methodologically weak, or unrelated to treatment outcomes.

The selection process involved sequential screening of titles, abstracts, and full texts, followed by the application of predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. This rigorous approach ensured that only high-quality and contextually relevant studies were incorporated.

2.2 INGREDIENTS: [7]

S.NO	TAMIL NAME	SCIENTIFIC NAME	ENGLISH NAME	QUANTITY
1.	Karuvangam	Tin	Plumbum	100 g
2.	Velvangam	Stannum	Stannum	100 g
3.	Rasam	Mercury	Hydragyrum	100 g
4.	Naagam	Zinc	Zincum	100 g

5.	<i>Ilupai</i>	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> Linn	Mahua	QS
6.	<i>Uthamani</i>	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> Linn	trellis-Ovine	QS
7.	<i>Kuppaimeni</i>	<i>Acalypha indica</i> Linn	Indian nettle	QS
8.	<i>Keezhanelli</i>	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> Schumach & Thonn	Bhumi Amla	QS

2.3 PURIFICATION

1. MERCURY:

- Grind the Rasam with brick powder, turmeric powder (*Curcuma longa* Linn), jaggery, spider web and *Arugam pul* (*Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers) separately for one day and rinse it off to get the purified form [8].
- Grind 35 grams of Rasam with brick powder and turmeric (*Curcuma longa* Linn) separately for 1 hour and rinse it with water. Afterwards, add 1.3 litres of *Kuppaimeni* juice (*Acalypha indica* Linn) to *Rasam* and burn it until all the moisture content of the juice evaporates [8].
- Squeeze the required amount of *Rasam* through a clean cloth for thousand times, put it in an earthen pot, add pure water which should be in an inch measure above the *Rasam* and heat it. Care should be taken that the water content should not be reduced. Once the water turns black, discard the water and rinse the *Rasam* with vinegar (Kaadi) for 4 - 5 times to attain complete purification [5].
- To 35 grams (1 balam) of *Rasam*, add 166 ml of *Tumbai Samoola* juice (*Leucas aspera* Linn) and insolate. Perform this process for 10 days with fresh juice on each day. Then dry it under sunlight until all the juice evaporates. Repeat this procedure for one more time. Then transfer this *Rasam* to an earthen pot, add 2.6 litres of *Tumbai* juice (*Leucas aspera* Linn) and lute it. Burry this for 20 days and then rinse the *Rasam* with water to get the purified form [5].
- Pour the *Rasam* into the deseeded chilli and daub the paste of *Kovai* leaf (*Coccinia grandis* Linn) of 4 finger breadth over this chilli. Lute it with 7 layers of cloth and incinerate it with 10 cow dung cakes (*Kukkuda pudam*) to get the purified form [5].

- Grind the *Rasam* with spider web, jaggery, *Thirikadugu*, turmeric, mustard, brick powder and salt separately and rinse it. Finally rinse it with *Oomathai* (*Datura metal* Linn) juice, curd and limestone water separately for 3 hours to get the purified form [9].
- Soak the *Rasam* in the latex of *Erukku* (*Calotropis gigantea* (L.) W.T. Aiton) for a day and grind it with brick powder, Spider web powder (*Pugaiyeeral*), turmeric powder (*Curcuma longa* Linn) and sugar to get the purified form. Then grind this *Rasam* with garlic to attain superior purification [10].
- Grind the *Rasam* with *Sengazhuneer* juice (*Nymphaea alba* Linn) to get the purified form [11].

2. PLUMBUM:

- Mix turmeric powder in the leaf juice of *Notchi* (*Vitex negundo* Linn). Melt the *Karuvangam* and pour it into the above mixture. Repeat the process twice to get the purified *Karuvangam* [8].
- Insolate the *Vangam* powder (35 g) with 210 ml of *Aiveli samoola* juice (*Diplocyclos palmatus* Linn) for 10 days. On next two days insolate it without adding juice and repeat this process once again. Then mix this *Vangam* in 5.3 liters of *Aiveli samoola* juice (*Diplocyclos palmatus* Linn) in a pot and lute it. Place it in a pit and fill it with cow dung ash. Take it from the pit after 20 days to get the purified form [8].
- Mix the *Karuvangam* powder in *Notchi* juice (*Vitex negundo* Linn) and insolate it to get the purified form [8].
- Mix the sesame oil with paste made out of goat's urine and *Pirandai* root (*Cissus quadrangularis* Linn). Melt and pour *Karuvangam* into this mixture. Rinse it off on cooling to get the purified form [5].
- Use Bandicoot feces to purify *Karuvangam* [5].
- Mix the *Pirandai* (*Cissus quadrangularis* Linn) paste in cow's urine. Melt and pour the *Karuvangam* into this mixture for 7 times to get the purified form [12].
- Melt the *Karuvangam* and pour it into sesame oil, cow's urine, vinegar (*Kaadi*), sour butter milk, horse gram's extract (*Macrotyloma uniflorum*) and latex of *Erukku* (*Calotropis gigantea* (L.) W.T. Aiton) separately to get the purified form [11].

- Melt 175 g of *Karuvangam* and pour it into sesame oil, horse gram decoction (*Macrotyloma uniflorum*) and limestone water separately for 5 times to get the purified form [11].
- Melt the *Karuvangam* and pour it into vinegar (*Kaadi*), Tamarind leaf juice, sour butter milk, *Aloe vera* Linn juice, cow's urine and sesame oil separately. Rinse it off well to get the purified form. Usage of hand mill stone for this process ensures the safety of person [13].

3. STANNUM:

- Mix turmeric powder in leaf juice of *Notchi* (*Vitex negundo* Linn). Melt and pour the *Velvangam* into the above mixture. Repeat the process twice to get the purified *Velvangam* [8].
- Insolate the *Velvangam* powder (35 g) with 210 ml of *Aiveli samoola* juice (*Diplocyclos palmatus* Linn) for 10 days. On next two days insolate it without adding juice and repeat this process once again. Then mix this *Vangam* in 5.3 liters of *Aiveli samoola* juice (*Diplocyclos palmatus* Linn) in a pot and lute it. Place it in a pit and fill the pit with cow dung ash. Take it after 20 days to get the purified form [8].
- Soak the *Velvangam* powder in leaf juice of *Notchi* (*Vitex negundo* Linn) and insolate it to get the purified form [8].
- Follow the same purification process of *Karuvangam* to get the purified *Velvangam* [5].
- Melt the *Velvangam* with sesame oil and pour it into the butter milk for 3 times to get the purified form [9].
- Mix *Navaatchaara* powder (Ammonium chloride) in Mahua oil. Melt and pour *Velvangam* into this mixture for 7 times. Then rinse it off with clean water to get the purified form [13].
- Melt and pour the *Velvangam* into vinegar (*Kaadi*), butter milk, cow's urine and lemon juice separately to get the purified form [11].

4. ZINCUM:

- Pour Mahua oil in a vessel and keep two pieces of *Navatchaaram* (Ammonium chloride) on either side of the vessel with partial immersion. Melt *Naagam* in an iron pan by the furnace and pour it into this oil for 21 times to get the purified form [8].

- Mix 4 ½ balam of the *Ruthraatcham* seed paste (*Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Roxb.) with 1 ⅛ balam of honey containing pollens of *Punnai* (*Calophyllum inophyllum* Linn), add 35 g (1 balam) of Nagam powder to this mixture and insolate it. This procedure is performed for 1 month to get the purified *Naagam* [5].
- Melt the *Naagam* with goat's ghee, pour it into the liquid concoction of child's urine, lemon juice and lime stone, and then burn it. This process is performed for 10 times to get the purified form [5].
- Make solution of oil cake (*Punnakku*) of *Iluppai* (*Madhuca longifolia* Linn). Melt the *Naagam* with Mahua oil and pour it into this solution for 7-21 times to get the purified form [9].
- Make the *Naagam* into a foil. Melt this foil and pour it separately into sesame oil, cow's urine and spurge milk (*Euphorbia ligularia* Roxb. ex Buch.) for 7 times to get the purified form [11].
- Pour Mahua oil into the mortar and cover it with the top stone of hand mill stone. Melt and pour *Naagam* through the hole of the hand mill stone. On cooling, rinse it off well. The process is repeated for 6 times to get the purified *Naagam* [11].

5. SANGU:

- Refine the Conch shell pieces by slaking it inside the heap of lime stone [5].
- Make a solution with equal amounts of Fuller's earth and limestone by adding 8 parts of water by volume. Boil the Conch shell in the supernatant of this solution, rinse and dry it completely [5].
- To 35 g of Conch shell, add 175 ml of juice of *Ilaikkalli* (*Euphorbia nerifolia* Linn) and insolate it. On next day, insolate it with fresh juice of *Ilaikkalli* (*Euphorbia nerifolia* Linn) again. Repeat this process for 3 times and rinse it off with water to get the purified form [5].
- Soak the Conch shell in butter milk of cow for 7 days to get the purified form [12].

2.4 PREPARATION:

Nagam (Zinc), *Velvangam* (Tin), *Karuvangam* (Stannum) are purified by melting and pouring in *ilupainei* (*Madhuca longifolia* Linn) for 10 repeated times and washed each time. This purified *Thiruvangam* is again melted and amalgamation is made with purified mercury (1/3rd part

or equal to the weight of the *Thiruvangam*). Now it is brittle, this is then placed in a *kalvam* & rubbed with *Veliparuthi* leaves (*Perugularia daemia* Linn) juice for 2 days, *kezhkainelli* (*Phylanthus niruri* Schumach & Thonn) leaves juice for 2 days and *kuppaimeni* (*Acalypha indica* Linn) leaves juice for 2 days and then made into thin cakes. This is enclosed in a pair of suitable mud pots and sealed with 7 layers of muslin cloth applied with clay at the junction of mud pots, dried and it is subjected to heavy incineration with about 300 cow dung cakes in a pit in an airtight compartment. After being cooled down the next day, if the medicine contains any metallic particles it is separated and fried with equal parts of *sangu* (conch shell) powder under immense fire. Thereafter both the powders are fried, powdered and then rubbed again in *kalvam* (motor) with *veliparuthi*, *kezhkainelli* (*Phylanthus niruri* Schumach & Thonn) and *kuppaimeni* leaves (*Acalypha indica* Linn) juice for 2 days respectively. cakes are made and it is subjected to heavy incineration as before, it now became fine white *chunnam* ready for use [7].

2.5 INDICATIONS: [7]

- Diabetes mellitus
- Diabetes insipidus
- Cancer
- Leprosy
- Ascites
- Liver and Spleen diseases
- Gonorrhoea
- Leucorrhoea
- Syphilis
- Ulcers
- Piles
- Fistula
- Kandamalai
- Carbuncles
- Peptic Ulcer
- Hemiplegia

2.6 TEST FOR CHUNNAM:

When a small quantity of *chunnam* (lime) is mixed with an equal amount of turmeric powder, the mixture develops a red coloration. This color change occurs due to the alkaline nature of *chunnam*, which reacts with the curcumin present in turmeric, thereby serving as a simple qualitative indicator of its alkalinity [14].

3 RESULTS:

3.1 Siddha Concept:

TABLE -1

INGREDIENT	TASTE	POTENCY	DIVISION	ACTIVITY
Karuvangam	Bitter	Hot	Pungent	Stimulant, Appetizer, Antiseptic, Astringent, Diuretic [5]
Velvangam	Bitter	Hot	Pungent	Antiseptic, Astringent, Sedative [5]
Rasam	All Taste	Based on Adjuvant	Based on Adjuvant	Alterative, Tonic, laxative, Diuretic [5]
Naagam	-	-	-	Astringent, Styptic Tonic [5]

TABLE – 2

INGREDIENT	TASTE	POTENCY	DIVISION	ACTION
<i>Ilupai</i>	Astringent	Hot	Pungent	Astringent, Stimulant, Tonic [15]
<i>Uthamani</i>	Bitter	Hot	Pungent	Expectorant, Anthelmintic, Emetic [15]
<i>Kuppaimeni</i>	Bitter, Pungent	Hot	Pungent	Anodyne, Anthelmintic, Cathartic, Diuretic, Emetic,

				Expectorant, Emmenagogue [15]
<i>Keezhanelli</i>	Astringent, Bitter, Sweet, Sour	Cold	Sweet	Deobstruent, Diuretic, Astringent, Coolant [15]

TABLE – 3

INGREDIENT	TASTE	POTENCY	DIVISION	ACTION
Sangu		-	-	Tonic, carminative, Astringent, Expectorant, Stimulant, Febrifuge Anodyne [5]

Table – 4

3.2 Scientific Concept

INGREDIENT	CHEMICAL COMPOSITION
<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> Linn	Madhunolic acid, 3',4'-dihydroxy-5,2'-dimethoxy-6,7-methylendioxy isoflavone, p-Hydroxyacetophenone, Hydroquinone, p-Hydroxymethylbenzoate, Ferulic acid, Madhushazone and Madhusalmone [16]
<i>Pergularia daemia</i> Linn	Daemine, uzarogenin, coroglaucigenin, steroids [17]
<i>Acalypha indica</i> Linn	Aurantiamide, Succinimide, Acalyphin, Kaempferol, Biorobin, Acalyphamide, and Nicotiflorin [18]

<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> Schumach & Thonn	phyllanthin, hypophyllanthin, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, alkaloids, ellagitannins, triterpenes, phenylpropanoid, steroids, ricinolic acid, niruricides, and filtetralin [19]
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3.3 PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIONS:

3.3.1 MADHUCA LONGIFOLIA

3.3.1.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

The antioxidant potential of *Madhuca longifolia* Linn was found to be comparable to butylated hydroxyl anisole, with *madhucic acid* identified as the key active compound. Antioxidant activity was assessed through reducing power, superoxide, and hydroxyl radical scavenging assays in vitro using a 70% ethanolic extract. In vivo evaluation involved CCl₄-induced hepatotoxic rats treated with the extract (200 and 400 mg/kg) and compared with silymarin (100 mg/kg). Parameters such as reduced glutathione (GSH), lipid peroxidation, wet liver weight, liver volume, and serum biomarkers including SGPT, SGOT, ALP, and bilirubin levels were measured, showing significant hepatoprotective and antioxidant effects of the extract [20].

3.3.1.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY

Inflammation, caused by mediators like histamine and serotonin, is regulated mainly through COX inhibition by anti-inflammatory agents. *Madhuca longifolia* Linn, traditionally used for inflammation, showed significant activity in Wistar rats when its methanolic extract was tested, confirming its potential as an anti-inflammatory remedy. Mahua seeds have demonstrated notable anti-inflammatory activity in the cotton pellet granuloma model. Similarly, a study reported that both the ethanolic extract of mahua and its isolated saponins effectively reduced inflammation in carrageenan-induced edema and cotton pellet granuloma models [20,21].

3.3.1.3 ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY:

Extracts of *Madhuca indica* Linn and *Madhuca longifolia* Linn (bark, leaves, and seeds) have shown significant dose-dependent antidiabetic and hypoglycemic effects in various experimental

models, comparable to glibenclamide. These effects are attributed to enhanced insulin release and improved glucose uptake [20].

3.3.1.4 WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

The inner pulp of *Madhuca longifolia* Linn fruit is used in cake preparation, while the outer portion is eaten raw. The fruits serve as an astringent, a lotion for chronic ulcers, and a remedy for tonsillitis. Mahua oil is widely utilized in cooking, margarine production, hair oil, soap making, and as fuel for lamps (Prashanth et al., 2010). The ethanolic extracts of Mahua bark and leaves have shown notable wound-healing activity by reducing the epithelization period and wound area. A 5% w/w ointment prepared from these extracts demonstrated wound-healing effects in excision wounds on experimental animals, comparable to the standard Betadine ointment [20].

3.3.1.5 ANTI-MICROBIAL ACTIVITY:

The methanolic extract of *Madhuca longifolia* Linn showed antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, while it was ineffective against *A. niger* and *Penicillium spp.*, and showed limited effect on *Scytilidium spp.* at higher concentrations [20].

3.3.1.6 IMMUNOMODULATORY ACTIVITY:

The flowers of *Madhuca longifolia* Linn are known for their tonic, aphrodisiac, astringent, and cooling properties. The ethanolic extract of mahua at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg body weight demonstrated significant immunomodulatory effects in cyclophosphamide-induced myelosuppressed mice. The extract improved the delayed-type hypersensitivity (DTH) response, increased antibody titre levels, and restored both total leukocyte count (TLC) and differential leukocyte count (DLC) [20].

3.3.1.7 NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

The ethanolic extract of mahua showed notable nephroprotective effects at doses of 500 and 750 mg/kg body weight against acetaminophen-induced nephrotoxicity. Treatment with the extract led to increased levels of serum urea, hemoglobin, total leukocyte count, creatinine, packed cell volume, differential leukocyte count, mean corpuscular volume, and body weight, while

simultaneously reducing neutrophils, mean corpuscular hemoglobin content, hematocrit, granulocytes, uric acid, and platelet counts [20].

3.3.2 PERGULARIA DAEMIA:

3.3.2.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Pergularia daemia Linn extracts have demonstrated strong antioxidant activity through DPPH, ABTS, and nitric oxide scavenging assays, with results comparable to standards like gallic acid and ascorbic acid. Ethanolic and methanolic extracts, rich in phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenols, and saponins, showed potent radical scavenging and peroxide suppression, indicating their potential as natural antioxidants [22].

3.3.2.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

Pergularia daemia Linn has demonstrated notable anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties with minimal adverse effects. Ethanolic extracts (200 mg/kg) significantly reduced carrageenan- and cotton pellet-induced paw edema in rats, inhibiting granuloma formation by up to 44.18%. In vitro studies using HRBC membrane stabilization also confirmed strong anti-inflammatory activity, comparable to diclofenac sodium. Additionally, aqueous and alcoholic root extracts showed significant analgesic effects in the hot plate test, while petroleum ether and chloroform extracts also exhibited comparable activity. These effects are attributed mainly to the presence of flavonoids and glycosides [22]

3.3.2.3 ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY:

Pergularia daemia Linn has shown significant anti-hyperglycemic activity in experimental models. At 300 mg/kg, its extract effectively reduced blood glucose in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats, with chloroform, ethanol, aqueous, and callus extracts all lowering glucose levels, in some cases more effectively than glibenclamide. Similar results were observed in alloxan-induced models, where alcoholic extracts produced a rapid and significant reduction in blood glucose, comparable to chlorpropamide. The hypoglycemic effects are attributed to bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, glycosides, triterpenes, saponins, phytosterols, tannins, and alkaloids [22].

3.3.2.4 HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

Ethanollic and aqueous extracts of *Pergularia daemia* Linn demonstrated significant hepatoprotective effects in CCl₄- and paracetamol-induced hepatotoxic rat models. At doses of 100–200 mg/kg, these extracts reduced elevated liver enzymes (SGOT, SGPT, ALP), bilirubin, cholesterol, lipid peroxidation, and malondialdehyde, while increasing total protein, albumin, and antioxidant markers such as glutathione. The protective effects are attributed to bioactive compounds, particularly flavonoids and triterpenoids, with quercetin-3-glucoside confirmed as a key constituent through HPTLC analysis. These findings highlight the role of *P. daemia* Linn flavonoids in mitigating hepatic damage [22].

3.3.2.5 DIURETIC ACTIVITY:

A study showed dose-dependent effect of *Pergularia daemia* Linn extracts, with the alcoholic extract at 400 mg/kg showing peak activity comparable to furosemide. Most extracts, except petroleum ether, significantly increased urine output ($P < 0.001$) and promoted sodium and potassium excretion, along with a slight rise in urine pH. These findings indicate that the diuretic effects of *P. daemia* Linn are likely mediated by bioactive secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, and steroids [22].

3.3.2.6 ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY:

Ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts of *Pergularia daemia* Linn demonstrated significant antibacterial activity against pathogens including *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *A. hydrophila*, *E. coli*, and *S. typhi*. Additional studies using hexane, chloroform, and ethyl acetate extracts of the leaves showed effectiveness against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. vulgaris* via the disc diffusion method, with the ethyl acetate extract being particularly potent. A novel bioactive compound, 6-(4,7-dihydroxy-heptyl) quinine, was isolated and identified as the key contributor to the antibacterial activity. A recent study evaluated the antifungal activity of *Pergularia daemia* Linn using the dry weight method to assess sensitivity and mycelial growth inhibition of keratinophilic fungi. The results indicated that *P. daemia* Linn salts were effective against *Aspergillus flavus* but showed no inhibitory activity against other tested pathogens, including *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Candida albicans* [23].

3.3.3 ACALYPHA INDICA

3.3.3.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Antioxidant potential of *Acalypha indica* Linn was evaluated by using a lipid peroxidation assay to measure its ability to inhibit oxidative damage in a previous study. The study revealed that the ethanolic extract exhibited a total antioxidant capacity of 442 nmol/g, while the aqueous extract showed a capacity of 338 nmol/g. These results indicate that both ethanolic and aqueous extracts possess significant antioxidant activity, with the ethanolic extract demonstrating a comparatively higher efficacy. This antioxidant activity is likely attributed to the presence of bioactive phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenols, and tannins, which can scavenge free radicals and prevent lipid peroxidation, thereby contributing to the plant's protective effects against oxidative stress-related cellular damage [24].

3.3.3.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

Multiple studies have highlighted the significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential of *Acalypha indica* Linn. Madhavan et al. reported that increasing concentrations of various plant extracts enhanced free radical scavenging activity, while methanolic extracts demonstrated superior antioxidant capacity compared to standard ascorbic acid using the DPPH assay. The antioxidant effects of *A. indica* Linn have been linked to its phytochemical content, particularly phenolic and flavonoid compounds, which act as radical scavengers, prevent lipid peroxidation, and may extend the shelf life of food products. Concentration-dependent antioxidant activity has been observed in acetone and ethanolic extracts, with acetone leaf extracts showing the highest phytochemical content relative to petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, and methanolic extracts. Aqueous-ethanolic extracts also exhibited significant anti-inflammatory effects, comparable to standard drugs such as diclofenac and ibuprofen, as demonstrated in albumin denaturation assays. Additionally, methanolic extracts showed dose-dependent anti-inflammatory activity and notable wound-healing effects when applied topically in rats, highlighting the therapeutic potential of *Acalypha indica* Linn in managing oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue repair [24].

3.3.3.3 ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY:

Studies have evaluated the anticancer potential of *Acalypha indica* Linn extracts against several cancer cell lines, including KB (oral cancer) and MCF7 (breast cancer), using Resazurin and MTT assays, with ellipsin and doxorubicin serving as reference standards. The methanolic extract showed limited activity against KB and MCF7 cells, as the inhibitory concentration exceeded 0.05 mg/ml. However, Sanseera et al. identified the phytochemical quebrachitol from *A. indica* Linn as responsible for anticancer activity against NCI-H187 (small cell lung cancer). The presence of similar bioactive compounds in both methanolic and ethanolic extracts suggests that these extracts possess potential anticancer properties, particularly against specific cancer types [24].

3.3.3.4 WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

Previous study demonstrated that the methanolic extract of *Acalypha indica* Linn promoted wound healing in rats without affecting their normal behavior or body weight, suggesting minimal pain and stress. The extract enhanced wound contraction, likely through increased fibroblast activity and collagen deposition, supported by its phytochemical constituents such as tannins. Its antimicrobial activity against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria further facilitated smooth healing. Wounds on limbs healed faster than those on the dorsum, likely due to thinner skin, and histopathology showed earlier epithelialization and enhanced angiogenesis, indicating that the extract effectively accelerated the overall wound healing process [24].

3.3.3.5 ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY:

The whole plant of *Acalypha indica* Linn has shown promising antidiabetic potential. Various extracts—hexane, acetone, petroleum ether, chloroform, and methanol–acetone—demonstrated significant activity, with hexane and chloroform extracts inhibiting alpha-amylase by 84.51% and 75.32%, respectively. Alpha-amylase breaks down starch into sugar, so its inhibition helps control blood glucose levels. In vivo studies in diabetic rats showed that oral administration of the plant extract reduced blood sugar by at least 25% and also lowered cholesterol, urea, and triglyceride levels. The extract may protect pancreatic β -cells, which is crucial for managing type II diabetes. Although traditionally only the root is used in India, studies indicate that using the whole plant is more effective, likely because the aerial parts contain more bioactive cyanogenic compounds [25].

3.3.4 *Phyllanthus niruri*

3.3.4.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Phyllanthus amarus Linn demonstrates strong antioxidant properties, supported by both in vitro and in vivo studies. Its extracts effectively scavenge free radicals, inhibit lipid peroxidation, and enhance the activity of endogenous antioxidant enzymes. These effects are largely attributed to its bioactive constituents, including ellagitannins, flavonoids, and gallic acid derivatives. Such antioxidant activity underpins its protective role against oxidative stress-related conditions, including liver injury, diabetes, obesity, and toxicity, positioning the plant as a promising candidate for nutraceutical and therapeutic applications [26, 27, 28].

3.3.4.2 ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

Phyllanthus amarus Linn extracts have shown notable anti-inflammatory effects in benzene-induced leukemia models. Treatment led to a reduction in TGF- β levels, indicating modulation of immune responses, limitation of fibrosis, and support for tissue repair. The extracts did not alter CRP, IL-8, or TNF- α levels, suggesting that they mitigate inflammation without triggering adverse immune reactions. These findings highlight the potential of *P. amarus* Linn as an adjunctive therapy in leukemia, meriting further mechanistic and clinical studies [26,27].

3.3.4.3 HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

Research indicates that *Phyllanthus amarus* Linn exhibits significant hepatoprotective and antiviral activity against hepatitis B virus (HBV). Ethanol extracts inhibit the growth of HBV-infected HepG2/C3A cells and reduce HBsAg levels in HepG2-NTCP cells, suggesting interference with viral replication and entry. Clinical studies also report therapeutic benefits in patients with mild to moderate alcoholic hepatitis. Additionally, *P. amarus* Linn protects against HCV-induced liver damage by enhancing antioxidant defenses, reducing lipid peroxidation, and preventing free radical-mediated injury. Molecular docking studies identify lignans and phyllanthin congeners as potential inhibitors of HCV NS3 protease, supporting its potential as a novel anti-HCV therapeutic [26,27].

3.3.4.4 NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY:

In rat models of diethylnitrosamine (DEN)-induced nephrotoxicity, *Phyllanthus amarus* Linn significantly improved kidney function markers and mitigated renal tissue damage. The nephroprotective effect is attributed to its ability to reduce oxidative stress and enhance antioxidant defenses, restoring parameters such as urea, creatinine, sodium, potassium, and chloride levels. These findings demonstrate its capacity to protect against chemically induced renal toxicity [26,27].

3.3.4.5 ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

In benzene-induced leukemia models, *Phyllanthus amarus* Linn extracts positively influenced hematological parameters. Methanolic extracts improved red blood cell indices, suggesting anti-anemic effects, while ethanol extracts modulated white blood cell counts, indicating immunomodulatory activity. However, all extracts prolonged clotting times, highlighting a potential risk of bleeding complications [26,27].

3.3.5 TIN and STANNUM:

3.3.5.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

The antioxidant potential of tin dioxide nanoparticles (SnO₂NPs) was evaluated using the DPPH assay, which measures free radical scavenging activity. DPPH, a stable purple radical, changes to yellow upon reduction, and the observed color shift in the presence of SnO₂NPs confirmed their scavenging activity. The extent of activity was concentration-dependent and occurred as a surface reaction. Particle size, morphology, and structural defects were noted as key factors influencing the antioxidant efficiency, suggesting the need for further studies to clarify these mechanisms [29].

3.3.5.2 ANTICANCER ACTIVITY:

The cytotoxicity of tin dioxide nanoparticles (SnO₂NPs) was tested on HCT116 and A549 cancer cell lines using particles of different sizes (8.85, 12.76, and 25.99 nm). Smaller nanoparticles showed stronger cytotoxic effects, with activity increasing in a dose-dependent manner. IC₅₀ values indicated higher potency of the smallest particles, while the *Piper nigrum* Linn seed extract

used for green synthesis was non-toxic. These findings suggest that smaller SnO₂NPs possess greater anticancer potential [29].

3.3.6 ZINC:

3.3.6.1 ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:

Superoxide dismutase (CuZn-SOD) is a key antioxidant enzyme that converts harmful superoxide radicals into hydrogen peroxide, which is then further broken down into harmless products. Being zinc-dependent, adequate serum zinc levels are essential to maintain its structure and function. Zinc deficiency impairs SOD activity, leading to increased oxidative stress and potential cell damage. Aging and certain infections reduce the activity of zinc-dependent enzymes like nucleoside phosphorylase and thymidine kinase, weakening cell membranes and increasing susceptibility to reactive oxygen species, thereby accelerating cell death and apoptosis. Zinc supplementation is therefore important for antioxidant defense and cellular protection [30].

3.3.6.2 IMMUNOMODULATORY ACTIVITY:

Zinc plays a vital role in maintaining immune health by supporting T cell function, natural killer (NK) cell activity, and the integrity of epithelial barriers in the skin, gut, and lungs. Deficiency in zinc impairs these immune defenses, leading to increased susceptibility to infections, particularly in older adults and individuals with certain conditions like acrodermatitis enteropathica or sickle cell anemia. Zinc supplementation has been shown to enhance T cell proliferation, improve innate and adaptive immune responses, and strengthen the body's overall resistance to infections, highlighting its critical role in sustaining effective immunity [30].

3.3.7 MERCURY:

Mercury and its compounds have been utilized for more than 3,000 years due to their diverse therapeutic properties. They have been applied as antiparasitic, anti-syphilis, antipruritic, preservative, anti-inflammatory, diuretic, and antibacterial agents. Additionally, mercury has been employed in dental amalgams as a restorative material, reflecting its longstanding medicinal and practical applications [31].

4 DISCUSSION:

The present systematic review comprehensively elucidates the pharmacological and therapeutic profile of *Thiruvanga Chunnam*, a classical Siddha metallo-mineral formulation. The formulation exemplifies the unique integration of metallic and herbal principles, highlighting the sophisticated pharmaceutics of the Siddha system, which has been practiced in Tamil Nadu for over three millennia. The meticulous processes of purification (*suddhi*) and incineration (*puta*) of metals and mercury not only ensure the safety of the final preparation but also enhance its therapeutic efficacy and bioavailability, aligning with traditional Siddha principles of drug standardization. The ingredients of *Thiruvanga Chunnam*—including mercury (Rasam), tin (Velvagam), stannum (Karuvagam), zinc (Naagam), *Madhuca longifolia* Linn, *Pergularia daemia* Linn, *Acalypha indica* Linn, and *Phyllanthus niruri* Schumach & Thonn demonstrate a broad spectrum of pharmacological activities. The review highlights that the metallic components contribute significantly to the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory properties. For instance, mercury exhibits longstanding anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and diuretic effects, while tin and stannum demonstrate antioxidant and anticancer potential, suggesting a synergistic role of metals in disease management. Zinc, as a cofactor for superoxide dismutase, not only enhances antioxidant defenses but also supports immunomodulation, reinforcing the clinical rationale for its inclusion in the formulation [30].

Madhuca longifolia Linn exerts hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, anti-diabetic, wound-healing, and immunomodulatory effects, consistent with its traditional use in managing systemic disorders. *Pergularia daemia* Linn offers antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, diuretic, and hepatoprotective actions, while *Acalypha indica* Linn demonstrates anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-healing activities. *Phyllanthus niruri* Schumach & Thonn complements the formulation with hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory activities. Collectively, these herbal constituents not only potentiate the therapeutic effects of the metallic components but also mitigate potential toxicities associated with heavy metals through chelation, biotransformation, and synergistic modulation of biochemical pathways.

Thiruvanga Chunnam exhibits extensive indications, ranging from metabolic disorders (diabetes mellitus and insipidus), infectious diseases (syphilis, leprosy, gonorrhea), liver and spleen

disorders, ulcers, piles, hemiplegia, and systemic inflammatory conditions, reflecting its broad-spectrum utility. The pharmacological evidence derived from both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies supports these traditional indications, particularly in modulating oxidative stress, inflammation, immune function, and cellular repair mechanisms. Notably, the dosage form's long shelf life up to 500 years and minimal effective dosage underscore its potency and stability, which is consistent with classical Siddha assertions regarding Chunnam formulations. Moreover, the combination of metallic and herbal ingredients in *Thiruvanga Chunnam* illustrates the Siddha approach of "herbo-metallic combination," where metals provide therapeutic potency and shelf life. This approach is reflected in modern pharmacological findings, wherein metals such as mercury and tin demonstrate cytotoxic and antioxidant activities, whereas herbs provide immunomodulation, hepatoprotection, nephroprotection, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects. This suggests that *Thiruvanga Chunnam* is capable of treating complex diseases with a reduced risk of toxicity when properly prepared and administered.

5 CONCLUSION:

This review provides scientific support for the traditional use of *Thiruvanga Chunnam* and highlights its potential as a therapeutic agent in modern integrative medicine. Future studies should focus on clinical validation, pharmacokinetic profiling, and mechanistic investigations to establish standardized protocols and safety parameters, thereby bridging classical Siddha wisdom with contemporary biomedical sciences.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATION:

Validation of *Thiruvanga Chunnam* through toxicological, pharmacokinetic, and randomized clinical studies is necessary for safe global acceptance.

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